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D2.2 Results of individual sessions with beneficiaries

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Introduction

The present deliverable elaborates the outcomes of the individual sessions conducted with beneficiary organisations of Widening projects established in Widening countries by the partners of the project. In some cases, WIDERA NCPs were leveraged by introducing beneficiaries of their countries to the partners of the project, responsible for conducting individual sessions.

Individual sessions are foreseen in Task 2.2 “Outreach” and are meant as an ongoing task until the M43 of the project.

Contributors of Task 2.2 were provided with promotional material describing the modus operandi of the WiderAdvance Facility, the services provided as well as a set of five questions contributing to the identification of valorization bottlenecks faced by beneficiaries of Widening actions.

1. Executive Summary

The activity of individual sessions with potential applicants to the widerAdvance Facility is an ongoing process. Their initiation is captured at the present deliverable. Individual sessions included introduction about the WiderAdvance Facility and (not always) a discussion on 5 questions identified as a proxy to valorization bottlenecks.

Individual sessions were conducted with **29 beneficiary organisations from 12 countries. The WiderAdvance Facility was introduced to beneficiaries of 94 unique Widening projects.** The majority of the projects related to Horizon Europe and represented notably Twinning (47), ERA Chairs (13), Excellence Hubs (9), European Excellence Initiative (7), Pathways to Synergies (6), Teaming (5), ERA Talents (4), ERA/Widening Fellowships (3), Support for R&I policy-making in the Western Balkans.

The work was divided according to the distribution table available at the project’s DoA, where each task contributor is usually responsible for more than one country. Following a mapping exercise delivered by the Work Package leader with the help of RUIZIA, all task contributors were handed with excel sheets per country of responsibility, containing beneficiaries of Widening actions and the projects involved. Then they contacted directly selected beneficiaries or with the help of WIDERA National Contact Points and arranged individual sessions.

An **overarching comment of potential applicants to the widerAdvance Facility** was whether direct funding is offered, whether non-technological results are eligible in the application, and whether, in case of organisations with multiple projects, the application needs central coordination. The most challenging issue was to convince applicants **of the benefits of the Facility** for the capacities of individual organizations and **how to transition from project-level to institutional level.**

By the responses in the **identification of bottlenecks**, it is evident that perception of valorisation is mostly **associated with patents (IP) and commercialization through spin-offs**. Anything other than that tends to be perceived as meriting neither dissemination, other than scientific publishing, nor exploitation. The beneficiaries interviewed indicated that they lack institutional capacity and specialized personnel. Furthermore, there is perceived lack of sequential funding leading to higher TRLs (4-7) which needs to be addressed at national level. In respect of **networking**, forging of sustainable collaborative networks with non-academic partners, outside projects, remains a challenge. The support of the EIT and innovation beneficiaries at national level was mentioned as a source of support with further potential.

Last, an obvious impression of the responses of the interviewees is that knowledge on valorisation is an intuitive, less structured process without any strategy.

The services offered by the widerAdvance Facility to those organisations comes to bridge the gap for a **consensus-based understanding on knowledge valorisation and cultivate progressively a consistent level of capacity within Widening beneficiary organisations**. The major tool is the **D&E academies** while the rest of the modular and individualized services with **IP, Negotiations, Standardisation, Preparation to match with Third Parties**, etc addressed the **lack of systematization and strategizing**. On the other hand, the **Matchmaking events and Open days, Study Visits, Coaching to access complementary funding and Mutual learning** come to bridge the gaps on (the purposeful) **access to non-academic networks** as well as **enhance understanding of the funding landscape and increase their chances for complementary funding**.

2. How work was structured for individual sessions

2.1. Mapping of widerAdvance potential beneficiaries

Based on the Dashboard, individual excel sheets were generated containing all **unique beneficiaries** of Widening projects, **participants and coordinators**, in relation to Widening projects of Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe. Ineligible projects were removed (Teaming phase 1 and IBA type of actions). In order to facilitate the selection of organizations for individual sessions by the project's partners, the excel file provided the following additional information:

- Legal entity name, type and PIC
- Role in a given project
- Project title & acronym
- Project status (signed/closed)
- Project start/closing date

- Topic description (of the call under which the project was financed)
- Topic code

The excel file gave a good overview on the type and volume of Widening projects won by each organization and under which capacity (coordinator/participant). Therefore, partners could select organisations based on the number and type of projects implemented, or vice versa.

2.2. Distribution table

The excel sheets were distributed to each partner according to the following table of the countries to be covered:

Partner	Type	Countries to be covered
IPPT PAN (PL)	REC	Poland, Ukraine, Romania, Serbia, Croatia
FORTH (EL)	NCP	Greece, Cyprus, Bulgaria
UNICO (CZ)	SME	Czechia
CVTI SR (SK)	NCP	Slovakia, Slovenia
EM (HU)	SME	Hungary
LMT (LT)	NCP	Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia
MHESR (TN)	NCP	Tunisia, Morocco, Turkey
SIPAC (AM)	NCP	Armenia, Georgia
SM (MT)	NCP	Malta, Montenegro, Kosovo, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Moldova, Faroe Islands, Albania
NEXA (FR)	Regional agency	French Outermost Regions
FCRT (PT)	Regional agency	Portuguese Outermost Regions + Portugal (continental part)
ACIISI (ES)	Regional agency	Spanish Outermost Regions

2.3. Promotional material used

Each partner had at its disposal **three** main promotional materials to convey information of the basic structure of the WiderAdvance Facility:

1. Providing overview of the Facility

How to apply?

1. Submit your application online - Launching 28 May 2025
2. Regular cut-off evaluations - Open Call runs until 2028
3. Receive your Service Delivery Plan - A customised roadmap for your organisation
4. Enjoy your path - Benefit from individual services and events
5. Follow-up & Impact tracking - We will share the success stories with our community

Ready to take your research further?
Apply today and unlock expert support to scale your results!

The Dissemination and Exploitation Facility for Widening projects
Advancing Result, Empowering Impact

Who Can Apply?
We're looking for committed organisations ready to scale their research results.

- EU-funded Widening action under Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe
- Supporting Key Exploitable Results directly or indirectly linked to Widening actions
- Organisations registered as legal entity in one of the Widening Countries or Outermost Regions

Eligibility criteria

Our Target groups

- Research Teams
- Research Managers and Administrators (RMAs)
- Technology Transfer and IP Officers
- Management of organisations

2. A short visual that additionally indicates the services

Free support for H2020 and Horizon Europe projects from Widening Countries & Outermost Regions

Who can apply:

- Organisations from Widening Countries and Outermost Regions
- Beneficiaries as coordinators of widening instruments
- Research Teams, Research Management and Administration

What you'll receive :

- Individual plan
- Indication which follow-up funding
- Start funded via DSI
- Links with industry, VCs, investors etc.
- Promotion of our achievements

Apply from 28 May

www.widerAdvance.eu

Funded by the European Union

3. An adaptable post especially developed for Ambassadors, containing a long version for LinkedIn, website, newsletter as well as a short version for X/Bluesky

2.4. List of questions to identify bottlenecks

Partners were provided additionally a list of 5 questions aiming to identify valorization bottlenecks they face in taking their research further.

1. Knowledge on valorization: Do you have a thorough understanding of research valorization options?
2. What are the main challenges you face when scaling-up your lab research? (funding, regulatory, difficulty in establishing collaborative networks)
3. How do you know whether the research results of your project have a market potential (to justify further development)?

4. Does your organization have an IP policy that helps in the valorization of your research?
5. Do you have collaborative networks with non-academic partners (within or outside your country)?

3. Individual sessions – projects approached

The partners reached out to almost all WIDERA NCPs in order to be referred to beneficiaries of Widening actions.

The beneficiaries of Widening actions that wished to find out more about the Facility they were referred to the partners of the project. The partners in turn explained the WiderAdvance Facility in relation to the projects implemented by those beneficiaries and particularly how they could access the services available by way of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) generated out of these projects.

The beneficiary organisations came from the 15 countries:

In the individual sessions with beneficiary organisations, the maturity and they type of project implemented influenced their perceptions of the potential benefits of the WiderAdvance Facility.

Distribution of unique projects in the individual sessions with Widening Beneficiaries

Status of projects (as of the 1st cut-off date)

Furthermore, the projects were characterized **empirically**, as **from the date of the 1st cut-off and in comparison to their duration**, as “New”, “Mature” when their remaining duration was up to 18 months, “Running” when they were below their first half of their duration, “Ending” when they would end within 2025 and “Closed”.

The list of **unique** Widening projects is available at the Appendix.

4. Comments of potential applicants to the widerAdvance Facility

The partners of the project faced certain “resistance” from the Widening beneficiaries during initial contacts or during individual sessions. These can be summarized as follows:

- How much funding is involved?

This was a very intuitive question, reflecting that applicants are not fully accustomed to receiving services instead of grants.

- Who implements the services? Information about the consortium

The wished to know if the service providers/coaches are knowledgeable enough and whether they have been used before by the European Commission.

- We heard about the Facility but it wasn't high enough in our agenda, too soon for us

In fact this was very frequent comment. On the one side, some potential applicants to the Facility initially rejected to be informed via an individual session on the excuse that they know their way around D&E. On the other, the focus was too project-based and planning outside this frame, especially, if subscribing to the Facility would require commitment of resources, was not within their immediate plans. In other instances, the Widening beneficiaries welcomed this opportunity but admitted that application would be considered at later cut-offs given that their project(s) had recently started.

- Our project has a small portion of research. Should KERs be only technological?

There was a challenge for teams to recognize what is a KER and for the project partners to guide them in this regard. In many cases it was explained that non-technological KERs which merit further Dissemination before they can be exploited by diverse actors, can be subject matter to some of the services of the widerAdvance Facility.

- What are the services? Do we need them?

Project partners explained the modularity of services, starting from D&E Academies as “workshopping” activities and for selected KERs, the Facility would provide more specialized services relating to IP, Strategy, Negotiations, Standardisation and Matchmaking. The individual services relating to the Protection of Intellectual Assets seemed to be very interesting to potential applicants to the Facility, probably due to the high cost associated with obtaining such services or employing dully specialized personnel.

- Will it help us with our D&E deliverables?

Again, this is associated to the “project-based” mindset of the applicants. Furthermore, the partners explained that it would help them produce more impact-oriented activities and deliverables

- Do we have to pay?

It seemed too generous of a service package to be offered for free

- Can non-academic institutions submit an application?

Some partners encountered this question during their contacts with Widening beneficiaries. The answer was yes, any beneficiary organization who has produced a key exploitable result from a Widening action.

- Can we decide at project level or at organization level?

It was made clear that the organization should apply. It was up to them to decide if the application would reflect KERs from many or few projects

- We need to contact the IP & Entrepreneurship vice-rector or a central unit

Teams implementing Widening projects found it equally useful that their hierarchy to have been informed by them and the WiderAdvance Facility.

- Can our organization submit at another cut-off?

Yes, but it will receive less priority

- Are the services of the Facility compatible with our institution's IP policy?

This comment came from well-informed organisations on IP and valorization in general.

- We believe that smaller organisations will benefit more from the widerAdvance Facility

This may be true as they are more flexible and may be in more need of the Facility's services towards institutional capacity building.

5. Outcomes of the questions identifying bottlenecks

Not all individual sessions with Widening beneficiaries gained concrete insights on bottlenecks to valorization. In total, 29 actors (beneficiaries of Widening actions) from 12 countries were interviewed on these bottlenecks.

Countries: Greece, Bulgaria, Poland, Romania, Croatia, La Reunion, Czechia, Estonia, Tunisia, Portugal, Malta, Montenegro

The outcomes are summarized below:

Q1: Knowledge on valorization: Do you have a thorough understanding of research valorization options?

Quote:

"Initially, [name of interviewee] admitted limited familiarity with the concept of valorization. Once defined as turning research into societal or market use, he acknowledged the systemic mindset barriers in [x country], particularly in nationally projects funded, where researchers believe that basic research must not have practical applications"

Those who have indicated a **basic knowledge**, declare that they never received formal training about research valorization and that their knowledge is mostly empirical focusing mainly on IP and spin-off creation, despite the existence, in some cases, of dedicated units within their host organisation. Even when valorization happens, it is rather an exception rather than the usual case. Some respondents indicated valorization as a synonym to scientific publications while in some instances, it was mentioned that feedback to policy and scientific communication might be considered as valorization options. Even when some respondents exhibit better understanding, they lack any practical experience and expressed their interest to be trained.

Those who indicated **"No"** tend to associate D&E exclusively with project-related obligations, while those who replied **"Yes"**, recognize the positive contribution of dedicated structures within their host organization (usually a university) as well as at national level. They tend to have collaborative relationships with non-academic partners, they recognize these connections as part of valorization and some of them have actual experience.

Q2: How do you know whether the research results of your project have a market potential (to justify further development)?

Quotes:

"Currently, market potential is usually identified through informal stakeholder engagement or staff experience, rather than a structured institutional process"

"a combination of market analysis, consultations with industry partners and experts, as well as pilot projects and prototype testing."

The majority of respondents admitted that they **do not rely on systemic processes** such as methodologies and tools. Instead, they rely on subjective opinions coming from the PI, the consensus from group meetings, as well as from the consultations of private partners from their collaborative networks. In some instances it was mentioned the expression of interest by a company as a green light to justify further development. Moreover, some blocking factors were mentioned such as the non-affordability of market analysis tools and the turnover of personnel.

Few admitted the use of tools and methodologies but still the market potential is assessed by non-systematic elements. Those who rely on the use of methodologies and tools use some of the following: **market potential analysis, growth prospects, unique selling proposition, secondary and primary market research, competitor analysis IP landscape**. Some admitted using a combination of tools, such as private partners' input, use of national infrastructures and publically-funded projects as test beds.

Q3:What are the main challenges you face when scaling-up your lab research (funding, regulatory, difficulty in establishing collaborative networks)?

Quotes:

“Support from our university or faculty in terms of exploiting research is minimal; publishing is often seen as the final step. Our Technology Transfer Office and project management team are both small, and

we lack institutional knowledge and access to training on investment, company formation, or commercialisation pathways. “

“Motivation of researchers is low (priority topics are publications and projects); valorisation or societal impact should become part of the researcher's performance review”

Only a small percentage indicated no challenge in scaling up their research due to clear IP policies and pathways. The majority of respondents indicated **multiple obstacles/challenges**. Respondents focused majorly on **funding gaps** at various stages of their research, on inadequate knowledge of project-based funding available, while others indicated that there is certain misalignment between funding schemes mainly targeting basic research and those targeting technologies beyond initial proof of concept, namely between 4-7. Moreover, some respondents indicated that private investors have a limited interest until a technology is validated (de-risked) while equity is not easily accessed in the order of up to 500.00 euros.

In respect of collaboration with the private sector, many respondents mention poor collaboration culture and not sufficient interest from the private sector in university technologies, as they may seem to them unattractive due to long(er) development cycles.

Institutional capacity as a major obstacle to scaling up of research was mentioned by many respondents in terms of limited knowledge on dissemination and exploitation, cultural perceptions and availability of specialized personnel (scientific, engineering and business) that is often needed.

Regulatory was a fraction of responses and majorly came from those engaged in health research.

Q4: Does your organization have an IP policy that HELPS in the valorization of your research?

Quote

“Support from our university or faculty in terms of exploiting research is minimal; publishing is often seen as the final step. Our Technology Transfer Office and project management team are both small, and we lack

institutional knowledge and access to training on investment, company formation, or commercialisation pathways. “

“Motivation of researchers is low (priority topics are publications and projects); valorisation or societal impact should become part of the researcher's performance review”

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Regulatory was a fraction of responses and majorly came from those engaged in health research.

Q5: Do you have collaborative networks with non-academic partners (within or outside your country)? If yes, are there any perceived inconsistencies or lack of industry interest?

Quotes:

“Although structures for collaboration exist, ... many are artificial or symbolic. Funding-dependent ‘ecosystems’ often fail to create

sustainable value and vanish when the money runs out. Industry, for its part, also lacks the maturity for strategic, long-term engagement”

“ we are relatively stronger in collaborations with SMEs than with large industry players. However, engaging industry - especially bigger companies - remains a challenge. There are inconsistencies in communication and expectations, and we have encountered difficulties in aligning academic and industrial timelines and objectives”

The majority of respondents indicated that they maintain collaborative networks with non-academic partners, within their country as well as outside. Few respondents emphasized sustained collaborative networks with local actors (i.e. La Reunion). However, these networks are not often based on solid collaboration agendas and are characterized by perceived misalignments with industry in timelines, objectives and capacity to absorb/co-create research results. It appears that SMEs are perceived as more open and flexible.

Few respondents implied that their collaborative network is under development and use for this end the EIT KICs, national support structures and innovation agencies. Some of them admit the need to build capacity in order to speak the same language with economic actors while others indicate that despite having contacts, they need support, because it is overwhelming for them.

Q5: Do you have collaborative networks with non-academic partners (within or outside your country)? If yes, are there any perceived inconsistencies or lack of industry interest?

Those who have implied that they **do not have a collaborative network**, they do not maintain contacts with non-academic partners, while others admit that they have networks within EU programmes, but once they finish, the collaboration is not sustained at all.

A main conclusion is that there is not a recognized need to cultivate mutual interest agendas for a sustained collaboration leading to less dynamic and transformational R&I ecosystems.

6. Correspondence between outcomes & Facility services

The outcomes of the individual sessions match perfectly with services of the widerAdvance Facility. Below follows a table highlighting important bottlenecks revealed and the features of the Facility.

<i>Bottleneck questions used in individual sessions</i>	<i>Bottlenecks identified individual</i>	<i>Matching with services of the WiderAdvance Services</i>	<i>Related WP</i>
<i>Q1: Knowledge on valorization: Do you have a thorough understanding of research valorization options?</i>	Lack of consensus on what is a Key Exploitable Result	D&E Academies, awareness raising webinars	1-2
	Valorisation mainly technological results	All basic service modules will support maturation of the adoption reading level of non-technological results	1-3
	Valorisation is meant mostly for IP protection and spin-off creation	D&E Academies will foster a commonly shared understanding of all valorisation options Awareness raising webinars on “D&E strategy of the EU”, “Open science and reproducibility”, Result dissemination for various stakeholders” “Knowledge transfer vs Technology transfer”	1-2

Q2: How do you know whether the research results of your project have a market potential (to justify further development)?

No planned process for systemic assessment of market potential of a research result

D&E Academy, namely:

1

1. Market Definition Canvas
2. Value Proposition Canvas
3. Characterisation Table
4. Exploitation Roadmap
5. Lean Canvas
6. Characterisation Table
7. Dissemination Strategy template

As well as services to selected KERs, such as

1. IP Strategy and Path to Commercialization

2. IP Negotiations

3. In-person assistance during face-to-face negotiation

Limited/non-affordable Tools & methodologies

D&E Academies in terms of basic service module (workshops) and modular services to selected KERs

1

Q3: What are the main challenges you face when scaling-up your lab research? (funding, regulatory, difficulty in establishing collaborative networks)

Funding gaps, limited knowledge on EU & national funding landscape

- Brokerage events matrix with indication on the type of TRL and adoption readiness level required.

2,3

Perceived misalignment of public funding towards TRL 4-7

- Coaching on Synergies
- Funding matrix
- Mutual learning workshops

Limited collaboration with private partners and limited interest with investors, different mindsets, not long-lasting networks

Matchmaking events and Open days

2,1

Brokerage events matrix

Preparation to match with third parties

Assistance with negotiation

Q4: Does your organization have an IP policy that HELPS in the valorization of your research?

Not helpful IP policy, not well articulated, lack of institutional capacities (TTO, KTO)

Study visits

2

Q5: Do you have collaborative networks with non-academic partners (within or outside your country)? If yes, are there any perceived inconsistencies or lack of industry interest?

Lack of “contractualisation” of relationships, not perceived need for establishment of agendas of mutual interest

Not common objectives

Only project-based

In process

Matchmaking events and open days (T2.5)

Study visits (2.6)

Preparation to match with third parties

IP Negotiations

In-person assistance during face-to-face negotiation

Dissemination strategy leveraging EIT / EEN

2,1

7. Next steps

Next steps are already planned and are configured as follows:

- Individual sessions

Continuation of individual sessions by all task contributors. Emphasis on countries that were not represented in the individual interviews such as Hungary, Cyprus, Slovakia, Slovenia, Lithuania, Albania, Kosovo, Spanish outermost regions

- Empower task contributors with:

- better understanding of the Facility (one2one meetings, collective capacity-building sessions)
 - **better articulation of benefits of applying to the Facility**
- reach out to WIDERA NCPs and cultivate a collaboration agenda to incorporate the widerAdvance Facility into their information events

8. APPENDIX – List of Widening projects

Below follows a list of Widening projects subject to individual sessions which introduced the widerAdvance Facility. Those horizontally highlighted are not unique projects (beneficiaries of the same project were interviewed).

COUNTRY	PROJECT	BENEFICIARY INSTITUTION	PROGRAMME	WIDENING CALL	LINK	Project Start Date	Project End Date	Months remaining as of 1st Cut-off	Status
GREECE	META-TOO	University of Athens (ETHNIKO KAI KAPODISTRIAKO PANEPISTIMIO ATHINON)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101160266	1/6/2024	31/5/2027	22	RUNNING
GREECE	NEXUS-MONARC	University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079156	1/1/2023	31/12/2025	5	ENDING
GREECE	SenseDiabetes	University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Fellowships	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101180598	2/1/2025	1/1/2027	17	NEW
GREECE	EXCEL4MED	University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101087147	1/1/2023	31/12/2026	17	MATURE
GREECE	ETHCSTWIN	University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101159928	1/6/2024	31/5/2027	22	MATURE
GREECE	ANDROMEDA	University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	Fostering balanced brain circulation - ERA Fellowships	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101130750	1/9/2024	31/8/2026	13	MATURE
GREECE	TransEET	University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101078875	1/1/2023	31/12/2025	7	ENDING
GREECE	FunShield4Med	University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079173	1/12/2022	30/11/2025	6	ENDING

GREECE	TALLHEDA	Agricultural University of Athens (GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON)	HORIZON EUROPE	European Excellence Initiative	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136578	1/1/2024	30/6/2027	23	RUNNING
GREECE	REENFORCE	Agricultural University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Talents	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101216708	1/9/2025	31/8/2029	36	NEW
GREECE	EU-CONEXUS ENABLES	Agricultural University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	European Excellence Initiative	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136822	1/2/2024	31/1/2029	42	NEW
GREECE	InPlasTwin	Agricultural University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101160289	1/10/2024	30/9/2027	26	NEW
GREECE	RACE	University of Crete (PANEPISTIMIO KRITIS)	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101176529	1/3/2025	28/2/2030	55	NEW
GREECE	TALOS-AI4SSH	University of Crete	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101087269	1/5/2024	30/4/2027	21	RUNNING
GREECE	TRIAD	University of Crete	HORIZON EUROPE	Pathways to Synergies (upstream)	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101158508	1/5/2024	30/4/2027	21	RUNNING
GREECE	TWIN4EarLiSt Age	University of Crete	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101159690	1/9/2024	31/8/2027	25	NEW
GREECE	ESPERANCE	Patras University (PANEPISTIMIO PATRON)	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101087215	1/2/2023	31/1/2028	20	MATURE
GREECE	METACITIES	Patras University	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101087257	1/1/2023	31/12/2026	17	MATURE
GREECE	MILESTONE	Patras University	HORIZON EUROPE	Pathways to Synergies (upstream)	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101159708	1/6/2024	31/5/2027	21	MATURE
GREECE	UMA3	Patras University	HORIZON 2020	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/952463	1/9/2020	31/8/2023		CLOSED

GREECE	PharmGenHUB	Patras University	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Western Balkans Special	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059870	1/7/2022	30/6/2025		CLOSED
GREECE	CHAngeing	University of Crete	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101087071/results	1/9/2024	31/8/2024		CLOSED
GREECE	DxHub	University of Crete	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101186531	1/1/2025	31/7/2027	24	NEW
GREECE	Edu4ClimAte	University of Crete	HORIZON EUROPE	Capacity building to strengthen networks of higher education institutions and cooperation with surrounding ecosystems	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101071247	1/10/2022	30/9/2026	14	MATURE
GREECE	WIDEnzymes	University of Crete	HORIZON EUROPE	Pathways to Synergies (upstream)	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101159534	1/1/2024	31/3/2027	18	MATURE
GREECE	METACITIES	P-NET ANADYOMENA DIKTYA NEAS GENIAS & EFARMOGES IDIOTIKI KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA (Competence center based in the city of Patras): PARTICIPANT	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101087257	1/1/2023	31/12/2026	17	MATURE
GREECE	DemosAxia	FORTH (IDRYMA TECHNOLOGIAS KAI EREVNAS)	HORIZON EUROPE	Pathways to Synergies (downstream)	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101160387	1/6/2024	31/5/2027	22	RUNNING

GREECE	BRIDGE	FORTH	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101160387	1/10/2022	30/9/2025	2	ENDING
GREECE	DYNASTY	FORTH	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079179	1/11/2022	31/10/2025	3	ENDING
POLAND	CREATE	INSTYTUT CHEMII FIZYCZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	H2020	ERA Chairs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/666295	1/10/2015	31/3/2021		CLOSED
POLAND	PERFECTION	INSTYTUT CHEMII FIZYCZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101186564	1/3/2025	28/2/2030	55	NEW
POLAND	TRIO-VI CoE	INSTYTUT CHEMII FIZYCZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	HORIZON EUROPE	Teaming for Excellence	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136570	1/1/2025	31/12/2030	65	NEW
POLAND	MitoPNP	UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI	H2020	Widening Fellowships	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101038064	1/9/2021	31/8/2023		CLOSED
POLAND	ENGHUM	UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI	H2020	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/692199	1/1/2016	31/12/2018		CLOSED
POLAND	TRAINCREASE	UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI	H2020	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/952324	1/1/2021	30/6/2024		CLOSED
POLAND	CONDEM	UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI	HORIZON EUROPE	Fostering balanced brain circulation - ERA Fellowships	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101130804	1/5/2024	31/10/2026	15	MATURE
POLAND	PATHFOOD	UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101160011	1/9/2024	31/8/2027	25	NEW
POLAND	SYNCC-IN	UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101159414	1/10/2024	30/9/2027	25	NEW
POLAND	AldesignTEX	POLITECHNIKA LODZKA	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Green Deal	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101159060	1/10/2024	30/9/2027	25	NEW

POLAND	SustDesignTex	POLITECHNIKA LODZKA	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079009	1/10/2022	30/9/2025	2	ENDING
CROATIA	AIFORS	University of Zagreb (SVEUCILISTE U ZAGREBU FAKULTET ELEKTROTEHNIKE I RACUNARSTVA)	H2020	ERA Chairs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/952275	1/1/2021	31/12/2026	17	MATURE
CROATIA	EXCELLABUST	University of Zagreb	H2020	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/691980	1/1/2016	31/12/2018		CLOSED
CROATIA	AeRoTwin	University of Zagreb	H2020	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/810321	1/9/2018	28/2/2022		CLOSED
CROATIA	MARBLE	University of Zagreb	HORIZON EUROPE	Teaming for Excellence	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136349	1/1/2025	31/12/2030	65	NEW
CROATIA	UWIN-LABUST	University of Zagreb	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101086340	1/1/2023	31/12/2027	29	MATURE
CROATIA	AeroSTREAM	University of Zagreb	HORIZON EUROPE	Capacity building to strengthen networks of higher education institutions and cooperation with surrounding ecosystems	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101071270	1/7/2022	30/6/2025		CLOSED
CROATIA	AloTwin	University of Zagreb	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079214	1/1/2023	31/12/2025	5	ENDING

CROATIA	InnoThyroGen	University of Split, Faculty of Medicine (SVEUCILISTE U SPLITU MEDICINSKI FAKULTET)	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101187880	1/1/2025	31/12/2028	41	NEW
ROMANI A	EU-CONEXUS ENABLES	Technical University of Bucharest (UNIVERSITATEA TEHNICA DE CONSTRUCTII BUCURESTI)	HORIZON EUROPE	European Excellence Initiative	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136822	1/2/2024	31/1/2029	42	NEW
ROMANI A	eHERITAGE	Transilvania University of Braşov (UNIVERSITATEA TRANSILVANIA DIN BRASOV)	H2020	Twinning	Expanding the Research and Innovation Capacity in Cultural Heritage Virtual Reality Applications eHERITAGE Project Fact Sheet H2020 CORDIS European Commission CORDIS European Commission	1/11/2015	31/10/2018		CLOSED
ROMANI A	AI4AGRI	Transilvania University of Braşov	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079136	1/10/2022	30/9/2025	2	ENDING
BULGARI A	TRANSTEM	Medical University of Varna	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/856871	1/10/2019	31/7/2025		CLOSED

CZECHIA	GeoUS	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	H2020	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/856670/results	1/1/2020	30/6/2023		CLOSED
CZECHIA	CESAR	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101186946	1/2/2025	31/1/2030	54	NEW
CZECHIA	EBEAM	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101087143	1/1/2024	31/12/2028	39	RUNNING
CZECHIA	MERGE	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101159582	1/9/2024	31/8/2027	25	RUNNING
CZECHIA	CLARA	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	HORIZON EUROPE	Teaming for Excellence	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136607	1/11/2024	31/10/2030	63	NEW
CZECHIA	TWIN SYNERGIES	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	HORIZON EUROPE	Pathways to Synergies (upstream)	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101160135	1/5/2024	30/4/2026	9	MATURE
CZECHIA	SAN4Fuel	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079384	1/11/2022	31/10/2025		CLOSED
TUNISIA	PRIMiNaS	CENTRE DE RECHERCHE EN MICROELECTRONIQUE ET NANOTECHNOLOGIE AU TECHNOPOLE DE SOUSSE	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079485	1/1/2023	31/12/2025	5	ENDING
ARMENIA	COBRAIN	YEREVAN STATE MEDICAL UNIVERSITY AFTER MKHITAR HERATSI	H2020	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/857600	1/10/2019	31/5/2023		CLOSED
ARMENIA	MaNaCa	INSTITUTE FOR PHYSICAL RESEARCH OF NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF ARMENIA	H2020	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/857502	1/10/2019	31/3/2023		CLOSED

ARMENIA	ARICE	YEREVAN STATE MEDICAL UNIVERSITY AFTER MKHITAR HERATSI	H2020	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/952417	1/9/2020	31/12/2023		CLOSED
ARMENIA	NanoQIQO	STATE EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENT OF HIGHER PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION RUSSIAN-ARMENIAN (SLAVONIC) UNIVERSITY	H2020	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/952335	1/1/2021	30/6/2024		CLOSED
ARMENIA	ETICA	AMERICAN UNIVERSITY OF ARMENIA FOUNDATION	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101187166	1/3/2025	28/2/2030	55	NEW
ARMENIA	NAR-SAR-IPH	L.A .ORBELI INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOLOGYOF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCESOF THE REPUBLIC OF ARMENIA STATE NON COMMERCIAL ORGANIZATION	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101087403/results	1/12/2022	30/11/2027	25	MATURE
ARMENIA	STREACS	AMERICAN UNIVERSITY OF ARMENIA FOUNDATION	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Green Deal	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101159235	1/6/2024	31/5/2027	22	RUNNING
ARMENIA	STREACS	NATIONAL POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY OF ARMENIA FOUNDATION	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Green Deal	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101159235	1/6/2024	31/5/2027	22	RUNNING
ARMENIA	STREACS	SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH INSTITUTE OF ENERGY	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Green Deal	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101159235	1/6/2024	31/5/2027	22	RUNNING

GEORGIA	CHARM-Vis	ILIA STATE UNIVERSITY	H2020	Widening Fellowships	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/867429	1/7/2019	30/6/2021		CLOSED
GEORGIA	ASCLEPIUS	GIORGI ELIAVA INSTITUTE OF BACTERIOPHAGY, MICROBIOLOGY AND VIROLOGY	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101159555	1/10/2024	30/9/2027	23	RUNNING
GEORGIA	GAIN	GEORGIAN TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101078950	1/10/2022	30/9/2025	2	ENDING
MALTA	ERA_SHUTTLE	UNIVERSITA TA MALTA	HORIZON EUROPE	Fostering balanced brain circulation - ERA Talents	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101120502	1/9/2023	31/8/2027	24	RUNNING
MALTA	EXCEL4MED	UNIVERSITA TA MALTA	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101087147	1/1/2023	31/12/2026	17	MATURE
MONTEN EGRO	MONTEVITIS	NATIONAL CONTACT POINT AT GOVERNMENT OF MONTENEGRO	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Western Balkans Special	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059461	1/1/2023	31/12/2025	5	ENDING
MONTEN EGRO	MONUSEN	NATIONAL CONTACT POINT AT GOVERNMENT OF MONTENEGRO	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Western Balkans Special	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060395	1/6/2022	31/5/2025		CLOSED
MONTEN EGRO	BCThubs	NATIONAL CONTACT POINT AT GOVERNMENT OF MONTENEGRO	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101087146	1/1/2023	31/12/2026	17	MATURE
MONTEN EGRO	CROSS-REIS	NATIONAL CONTACT POINT AT GOVERNMENT OF MONTENEGRO	HORIZON EUROPE	European Excellence Initiative	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136834	1/1/2024	31/12/2028	41	NEW

MONTENEGRO	POLICY ANSWERS	SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY PARK MONTENEGRO (NAUCNO - TEHNOLOSKI PARK CRNE GORE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Support for R&I policy making in the Western Balkans	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058873	1/3/2022	28/2/2026	7	MATURE
PORTUGAL	CHAngeing	UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101087071	1/1/2023	31/12/2026	17	MATURE
PORTUGAL	MIA-Portugal	UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA	HORIZON 2020	Teaming Phase 2	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/857524	1/1/2020	31/12/2027	29	MATURE
LA REUNION	REALISTIC	UNIVERSITE DE LA REUNION	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101086690	1/12/2022	30/11/2027	28	MATURE
LA REUNION	TwinSolar	UNIVERSITE DE LA REUNION	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101076447	1/9/2022	30/11/2025	4	ENDING
LA REUNION	FOCUS-4R	CYROI	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Talents	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101076447	1/9/2025	31/8/2029	47	NEW
ESTONIA	BALTIC-FIT	Talltech (TALLINNA TEHNIKAÜLIKOO)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Green Deal	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101159424	1/9/2024	31/8/2027	25	RUNNING
ESTONIA	MarTe	Environmental Investment Center (SIHTASUTUS KESKKONNAINVESTERINGUTEKESKUS)	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101186498	1/1/2025	31/12/2028	41	NEW
ESTONIA	OH-BOOST	University of Tartu (TARTU ULIKOOL)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079349	1/1/2023	31/12/2025	5	ENDING
UKRAINE	BIONANOSENS	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	H2020	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/951887	1/10/2020	31/5/2024		CLOSED

UKRAINE	NEUROTWIN	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	H2020	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/857562	1/8/2019	31/7/2022		CLOSED
UKRAINE	BRIDGE	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Green Deal	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101160337	1/9/2024	31/8/2027	25	NEW
UKRAINE	AGRI-BIOCIRCULAR-HUB	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101186869	1/1/2025	31/12/2028	42	NEW
UKRAINE	HELIOS	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Green Deal	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101155017	1/10/2024	30/9/2027	26	NEW
UKRAINE	ECOTWINS	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079308	1/10/2022	30/9/2025	2	ENDING
UKRAINE	SURE-AMR	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101160053	1/10/2024	30/9/2027	26	NEW

UKRAINE	TWISMA	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101078960	1/1/2023	31/12/2025	5	ENDING
UKRAINE	ECOTWINS	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079308	1/10/2022	30/9/2025	2	ENDING
UKRAINE	EDUC-WIDE	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	European Excellence Initiative	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136533	1/3/2024	28/2/2027	19	RUNNING
UKRAINE	APPROACH (mutiple participation)	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Fostering balanced brain circulation - ERA Talents	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101120397	1/6/2023	30/11/2026	16	MATURE
UKRAINE	WaterWise Hub (mentoring under mentoring scheme)	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101184151	1/1/2025	31/12/2028	43	NEW
UKRAINE	WIDE AcrossEU	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Pathways to Synergies (upstream)	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101158561	1/5/2024	31/8/2027	25	RUNNING

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